

RECENT ADVANCES IN LAWS AND ETHICS IN ORGAN TRANSPLANT IN INDIA-A REVIEW

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Abstract:

The legislation called transplantation of human organ act (THO) was passed in India in the year 1994. In the rules has been accepted brain death as a mode of death and sale of organ is a punishable offence where still now many cases are reported of organ transplant. Through section 9(3) of THO, it is mentioned unrelated donor can donate their organ through signing in a consent form and the scandals are happening based on this. THO has undergone major and minor changes in the form of addition of rules and amendments in order to improve the acts to make it much acceptable legally. In recent years' cadaveric organ transplant has been increased. Organ scarcity is still a global problem, to solve that problem some hospitals, NGOs (like MOHAN), United Network of Organ Sharing (UNOS) are keeping momentum of deceased disease programme. In 2008 Governments amend few new amendments on a purpose of putting a stop to organ commerce. The legal and ethical principles that we follow universally with organ donation, transplantations are also important for the future as these may be used to resolve our conflicts related to emerging sciences such as cloning, tissue engineering, and stem cells.

Keyword: Ethics in organ transplant, Cadaveric Transplantation, Organ Donor.

Introduction:

Organ transplant is one of the biggest medical marvels of the twentieth century, which has prolonged and improved the lives of hundreds of thousands lives in the whole world. (1) Organ transplant is the only lifesaving treatment in case of end stage organ failure. Organ scarcity is a global concern (1). Organ donation is a global issue and cadaveric organ donation can solve this problem. Kidney transplant has started in India in 1970 (2). India is a leading country in the organ transplantation. First 10 years India has faced

surgical problems, immunosuppression and ethical issues. The ethics of transplants in India has always been on a slippery slope and all kinds of nefarious activities were accepted as normal practice. In the next 10 years many illegal organ transplant scandals happens where the THO was criticized globally in many places. The pressure on the Government saw the passing of the Transplantation of Human Organ Act (THO) legislation that made unrelated transplants illegal and deceased donation a legal option with the acceptance of brain death (3). The organ donating scandal was so strong in India that it was very tough to start the cadaveric organ donation. The family members of brain death patients are not willing to donate the patient's organ. In most instances, the donor accused the recipient or the middle man of having not compensated them with the promised sum. The history of cadaver transplants in India is recent, the first attempts to use a cadaver donor's kidney were undertaken in 1965 in Mumbai. (2). That time doctors have faced many problems including technical, immunological and infections. The whole process was described by the authors. This was a setback for the cadaver program for not only Mumbai but also rest of the country. (4)

The deceased donor donation rate in India stands at around 0.34 per million, which is abysmally low when compared to the organ donation rate prevalent in other developed countries. (5) In the Indian scenario, many cultural and religious beliefs influence the decision making regarding deceased organ donation. Lack of awareness (80.1%), religious beliefs and superstitions (63.4%), and lack of faith in the healthcare system (40.3%) have been believed to be the most important reasons for the family members refusing for giving their consent for organ donation of their close relatives. (6)

Asian countries are bound to socio religious factors that's why it's very tough to make a conversation about the organ donation of a brain death patient. After several awareness program some educated people are willing to donate their organ after death, but that number is so small with respect to the need. Superstition is another big problem in India. Many people believe in soul, rebirth and that is causing a big problem in organ donation (7) Lack of effective conversation and lack of effective communications after death is causing a big problem in organ donation.

According to Mohan foundation, each day 15 patients die in the waiting for an organ. From 1990 to 2000, number of patients on the transplant waiting list has increased by 14 % per year while increase in donors has increased an average 3 % per year. National and Tissue transplant organization is a national level organization set up under the Directorate General of Health Services, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. The National Human Organ and Tissue Removal and Storage Network is a subdivision of this organization, which was formed as mandated by the Transplantation of Human Organ Act (THOA) amendment in 2011. This is established in Delhi and will gradually expand to involve other states and regions of the country. It functions as an apex centre for conducting all India activities related to coordination and networking, for the procurement and distribution of organs and tissues, for maintaining the registry of organs, and for facilitating tissue donation and the transplantation of the harvested organs across the country.

METHODS: We have taken some recent papers which is mostly published after 2005 and reviewing all the paper to understand the problems and solution in both the aspect ethically

and medically in India. As organ transplantation is more bound to ethical issues so we are concentrating on ethical issues in much deeper way.

THE EVOLUTION OF LAW:

Transplantation of Human Organ Bill was introduced in the Lok Sabha on 20th August 1992. Transplantation of Human Organ Act (THOA) was passed in 1994. This is the primary legislation related to organ donation and transplantation in India. Before the introduction of this Act, the regulations for organ donation and transplantation in India were non-existent and malpractices were rampant. The amendment to the Act was passed by the parliament in 2011, and the rules were notified in 2014 as the Transplantation of Human Organs and Tissue Rules – 2014 (8)

For living donors, it is important to see who can donate without any legal problems. The relative who are allowed to donate are father, mother, brother, sister, son, daughter, spouse. Recently in the gazettes, grandparents are included. The donor has to prove his or her identity and have to prove the relation with the patient through genetic testing or legal documents. In this case donor will not get any money.

Brain-death and its declaration - brain death is defined by the following criteria: two certifications are required 6 hours apart from doctors and two of these have to be doctors nominated by the appropriate authority of the government with one of the two being an expert in the field of neurology.

Regulation of transplant activities by forming an Authorization Committee (AC) and Appropriate Authority (AA.) in each State or Union Territory. Each has a defined role as follows: (1) (2)

- a. Role of Authorization Committee (AC) - The purpose of this body is to regulate the process of authorization to approve or reject transplants between the recipient and donors other than a first relative. The primary duty of the committee is to ensure that the donor is not being exploited for monetary consideration to donate their organ. The joint application made by the recipient and donor is scrutinized and a personal interview is essential to satisfy to the AC the genuine motive of donation and to ensure that the donor understands the potential risks of the surgery. Information about approval or rejection is sent by mail to the concerned hospitals. The decision to accept or reject a donor is governed by Sub Clause (3), Clause 9 of Chapter II of the THO act.
- b. Role of Appropriate Authority (AA): The purpose of this body is to regulate the removal, storage, and transplantation of human organs. A hospital is permitted to perform such activities only after being licensed by the authority. The removal of eyes from a dead body of a donor is not governed by such an authority and can be done at other premises and does not require any licensing procedure. The powers of the AA include inspecting and granting registration to the hospitals for transplant surgery, enforcing the required standards for hospitals, conducting regular inspections of the hospitals to examine the quality of transplantation and follow-up medical care of donors and recipients, suspending or cancelling the registrations or erring hospitals, and conducting investigations into complaints for breach of any provisions of the Act.

The AA issues a license to a hospital for a period of 5 years at a time and can renew the license after that period. Each organ requires a separate license.

The relevant statements related to the deceased donor transplantation from the Transplantation of Human Organs and Tissue Rules – 2014 are discussed in brief.(2)

Section 3 - Authority for removal of human organs or tissues

A living person may authorize the removal of any organ or tissue of his or her body during his or her lifetime according to the prevalent medical practices.

Section 4 - Panel of experts for brain-stem death certification

The appropriate authority shall maintain a panel of experts to ensure an efficient functioning of the Board of Medical Experts and it shall remain fully operational at all times.

Section 5 - Duties of the registered medical practitioner

The registered medical practitioner of the hospital in consultation with the transplant coordinator, if available, shall ascertain, after certification of brain death of a patient in the intensive care unit, from his/her near relative or, if near relative is not available, then, any other person related by blood or marriage, and in case of an unclaimed body, from the person in lawful possession of the body, namely:

5.1(a) - that the person in the presence of two or more witnesses (at least one of whom is a near relative of such a person) had authorized before his/her death, as specified in form no. 7 or other documents like driving license, etc., the removal of his/her organs after death and he/she has not revoked the above said authorization.

5.1(b) - if authorization was not made by the person to donate the organs after death, then the registered medical practitioner in consultation with the transplant coordinator, shall make the near relative or person in lawful possession of the body, aware of the option to authorize or decline the donation and an authorization to this effect shall be ascertained as per Form 8 to record the status of consent, and in case of an unclaimed body, the same shall be made in Form 9 by the authorized official.

5.1(c) - after authorization and consent is given, the registered medical practitioner through the transplant coordinator informs the authorized registered Human Organ Retrieval Centre through an authorized coordinating organization by available documentable mode of communication.

5.2. The above-mentioned duties also apply to the registered medical practitioner working in an Intensive Care Unit in a hospital not registered under this Act.

5.4 – A registered medical practitioner, before removing any organs/tissues from the body of a person after death, should in consultation with the transplant coordinator ensure the following, namely, that the authorization has been given as specified and the same has not been revoked, and the consent of the near relative or person in lawful possession of the body shall also be required notwithstanding the authorization been made by deceased

donor. Provided that if the deceased person who had earlier given authorization but had revoked it subsequently, and if the person had given in writing that his organ should not be removed after his death, then, no organ or tissue will be removed even if consent is given by the near relative or person in lawful possession of the body.

5.5(b) - that the near relative of the deceased person or the person lawfully in possession of the body of the deceased donor has signed the declaration, as specified in Form 8.

5.5(c) – In the case of brain-stem death of the potential donor, Form 10 has been signed by all the members of the Board of Medical Experts. Provided that where a neurologist or a neurosurgeon is not available, an anaesthetist or intensivist who is not a part of the transplant team nominated by the head of the hospital duly empanelled by Appropriate Authority may certify the brain stem death as a member of the said Board.

5.5(d) In the case of brain-stem death of a person of less than eighteen years of age, Form 10 has been signed by all the members of the Board of Medical Experts and an authority as specified in Form 8 has been signed by either of the parents of such a person or any near relative authorized by the parent.

Section 6 - Procedure for donation of organ or tissue in medico-legal cases

6.1 - After the authorization and consent are obtained, the registered medical practitioner of the hospital should make a request to the Station House Officer or Superintendent of Police or Deputy Inspector General of the area either directly or through the police post located in the hospital to facilitate timely retrieval of organs or tissue from the donor and a copy of such a request should also be sent to the designated post mortem doctor of the area simultaneously.

6.2 - It should be ensured that by retrieving organs, the determination of the cause of death is not jeopardized.

6.3 - The medical report in respect of the organs/tissues being retrieved should be prepared at the time of retrieval by the retrieving doctor and should be taken on record in post-mortem notes.

6.4 - Wherever it is possible, attempt should be made to request the designated post-mortem registered medical practitioner, even beyond office timing, to be present at the time of organ or tissue retrieval.

6.5 - In case a private retrieval hospital is not doing post mortem, they should arrange transportation of body along with medical records, after organ or tissue retrieval, to the designated post-mortem centre and the post mortem centre should undertake the post-mortem of such cases on priority, even beyond office timing, so that the body is handed over to the relatives with least inconvenience.

Section 8 - Removal and preservation of organs or tissues

The removal of the organs/tissues should be permissible in any registered retrieval or transplant hospital or centre and preservation of such organs/tissues should be ensured in registered retrieval or transplant centre or tissue bank according to current and accepted

scientific methods in order to ensure viability for the purpose of transplantation.

Section 9 - Cost for maintenance of cadaver or retrieval or transportation or preservation of organs or tissues

The cost for maintenance of the cadaver, retrieval of organs, their transportation and preservation, should not be borne by the donor family and may be borne by the recipient or institution or Government or non-Government organization or society, as decided by the respective State Government or Union territory Administration.

Section 32.8 - Pledge for organ or tissue donation after death

Those persons, who, during their lifetime have pledged to donate their organs/tissues after their death, shall in Form 7 deposit it in the paper or electronic mode to the respective networking organization/institution where the pledge is made, who shall forward the same with the respective networking organization and the pledger has the option to withdraw the pledge through intimation.

Discussion:

Organ transplantation is very important and everyone should participate in this noble work. Deceased donor the most important organ donor. Deceased donor is divided into two parts. One is brain death donor and another is cardiac death donor. In India Cardiac death donor are not considered due to legal issues.

Brain death is divided into three parts, Coma, absence of brain stem reflex and apnoea. Candidates should be norm thermic (core temperature $\geq 36^{\circ}\text{C}$), stable hemodynamically (systolic pressure ≥ 90 mm Hg), free from sedative and paralytic drugs with normal oxygenation and near normal PaCO₂. If respiratory movements are not present and the PaCO₂ is >60 mm Hg or elevated >20 mm Hg from baseline value, the test is considered positive (9)

Apnoea should be done two times in a 6 hours interval by a group of 6 doctors where two doctors will be neurologists working in government hospital. If a neurologist or neurosurgeon is not available, then an anaesthetist can declare brain death.

Additional tests are not required to confirm brain death as per the American Association of Neurology (AAN) guidelines. In patients in whom a complete clinical examination cannot be done, however, ancillary testing can be used to confirm brain death such as *cerebral angiography, cerebral scintigraphy, isotope angiography, transcranial Doppler ultrasound and electroencephalogram*. The AAN also recommends that the physicians should be wary about the false positive results and may choose not to proceed with declaration of brain death rather than ordering these ancillary tests in case of unreliable clinical findings(10,11)

Standard and extended criteria: Donor age may be more than 50, death can be due to hypertension or Cerebrovascular accident and terminal creatinine $>1.5\text{mg/dl}$

Scoring System is mostly used for kidney transplant. Kidney donor profile index” (KDPI) was approved by the Organ Procurement and Transplantation Network Kidney

Transplantation Committee in 2013, to estimate the risk of post-transplant kidney graft failure from a particular deceased donor kidney relative to other kidneys. The KDPI score includes the donor's age, height, weight, ethnicity, serum creatinine level, history of diabetes, history of hypertension, hepatitis C status, cause of death, and whether the donation would occur after cardiac death. Each kidney is scored in a KDPI spectrum from 0% to 100%. Lower scores are accepted to have a longer potential function of the donor organ than those with higher scores.(12)

The deceased donor score was determined from five donor variables obtained at the time of procurement. The variables were donor age (0-25 points), history of hypertension (0-4 points), creatinine clearance (0-4 points), human leukocytic antigen (HLA) mismatch (0-3 points), and cause of death (0-3 points), with the total number of points ranging from 0-39. A grade (A to D) was then assigned to the specific deceased donor based on his cumulative score. Greater than 20 points or grades C and D were defined as marginal donors with a much shorter potential function of the donor organ.(13)

Organs are transported in a packed ice box, where temperature are shown and the temperature should be maintained. In India, green corridor transportation is used. Otherwise helicopter is the based method to transport organs.

Body is buried or burned as per rituals and believe.

Organ shortage is a global programme. Demand is always very high but organ supply is very less. HIV and Cancer organs are not considered.

Organ scandal is also a big problem. The World Health Organization (WHO) in its statement on the sale of organs clearly states that it violates the Universal Declaration of Human Rights as well as its own constitution: "The human body and its parts cannot be the subject of commercial transactions. Accordingly, giving or receiving payment... for organs should be prohibited." The WHO advises physicians not to transplant organs "if they have reason to believe that the organs concerned have been the subject of commercial transactions."(14)

So, in India more awareness is needed on this topic. Still now on an average 15 patients are dying in India during the waiting period.

Conclusion: 26 years ago, THO was passed in India but still now organ scandal is going on. The effective changes are coming on this global issue but people believe, superstitions are affecting to reach the target. India is a secular country, so it's very difficult to do the awareness programme. NGO like Mohan and some hospitals are really helping in this matter, but poor socioeconomic background, low education, superstitions are causing problems.

Heart is preserved for 4 hours, lungs 4 to 6 hours, liver 6 to 10 hours, pancreas 10 to 12 hours, intestines 6 to 12 hours, kidney 24 hours. So proper transportation is important.

In future hope we can take living organs from friends also if they are willing to donate and if MHC, ABO grouping, RH factors, immunologic factors, lymphocytic factor matched. And in near future we can take organ from cardiac death deceased patients. Then the scarcity will be reduced and much more awareness program should be considered in this matter.

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